

Interview With Christine Sinicki

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On Friday the 24th, I met with State Representative Christine Sinicki who represents Wisconsin's 20th district at La Finca Cafe in St. Francis. I had plenty of questions for her, and she was incredibly helpful throughout. State Representative Sinicki defines homelessness, or as she refers to it more properly unhoused, as "A person or family that is unhoused" and may or may not have the funds or skills necessary to gain housing. This closely mirrors the OHCHR (The Office of the High Commissioner of Human Rights) definition of homelessness, "experiencing homelessness means not having stable, safe and adequate housing, nor the means and ability of obtaining it." She also said that she's noticed that many unhoused are families or younger to middle aged men. This statement agrees with the 2024 HUD (Department of Housing and Urban Development) report on homelessness, which states that unhousedness in families has increased by 39.4% and among individuals by 9.4% from 2023-2024. Young to middle aged people (for the sake of this article is 18-54) make up 61.8% of the unhoused population. Of all unhoused people, 59.6% describe themselves as male, which is a statistic that also supports Rep. Sinicki's claim. She also says that single women with children are highly exploitable and more likely become homeless because these women are often young and caring for one or many children, and, with only one source of income, it is incredibly difficult to maintain a steady living. She also finds that these women are highly exploitable because they need the money in order to provide for their family and will work for very low wages. While we were discussing the groups affected by unhousedness, she also brought up the often overlooked student unhoused issue which she describes as a noticeable issue in Milwaukee. She stated that, "while I can't give a percent or number, (of unhoused students because the schools do not provide information on the amount or who are unhoused, in the interests of those students) it is pretty easy to tell what vans that students are taking are for shelters". She also said that this overall increase of unhousedness in Milwaukee specifically is attributed to the continual rise in housing prices and rent over the last several years.

I brought up the discussion of what resources unhoused people have, and Rep. Sinicki was a keen supporter of an organization called Housing First, which, as the name suggests, primary priority is providing housing for the unhoused. The organization holds the philosophy that housing is a prerequisite for an individual's economic success and development. She says that the goal is to get the unhoused off the streets so that they can be successful. While we were discussing unhoused encampments in Milwaukee, she noted that unhousedness also leads to increases in crime in the areas that they are often taking refuge. She attributes this to the fact that many unhoused have substance abuse issues or mental health problems and struggle to receive or simply don't receive proper treatment. While unhoused often do have ulterior issues that cause unhousedness, she also noted that there are many unhoused who work for time jobs or multiple jobs but simply cannot afford housing. While individuals struggle to achieve the funds to gain access to housing,

Rep. Sinicki also said that Housing First struggles to have access to funding that would allow it to enact its projects on a larger and more effective scale. She said that she has recommended that Governor Evers implement a \$250k funding of Housing First in this year's Wisconsin state budget proposal. Rep. Sinicki said that bills addressing unhousedness at the state level are very partisan and that she often finds that the Wisconsin Republican Party puts together 'show bills' in order to allow them to make the claim that they tried to address these issues. Show bills refer to bills that a

party, the Republican Party in this instance, put together and propose but fully intend on killing or intentionally preventing the bill from passing in order to allow them to make a claim or make a media stunt of some sorts. The bill that me and her discussed was 2023 Wisconsin Assembly Bill 689, which primary purpose was to designate a “pay for performance” program where recipients of grants meant for the purpose of reducing unhousedness would only receive the full funds of the given grant if they prove to increase the amount of unhoused who gain permanent housing, employment full or part time and or prevent unhoused from returning to a state of unhousedness. The discretion of how the funds would be distributed was up to the decision of the DOA (Department of Administration). The fiscal estimates for the proposed bill was \$586,800 which were prepared and released by the DOA. Bill 689 would pass through the Wisconsin state assembly; however, when it arrived at the senate with a joint resolution, the bill would die. She said that the Wisconsin Democratic Party has plans for this fiscal year to attempt to push through bills regarding housing and lowering eviction rates in the state. She also said that many who are homeless are often weary of receiving government assistance because some don't want the government to involve itself in their lives, and this is often because they're afraid of living under the thumb and control of a government agency. She said that much of the unhoused issue falls upon the county because largely state governments are not proactive in fighting the issue and that this especially applies to the federal government. While the federal government has tremendous power to fight unhousedness, they primarily use Block Grants as a way to address these issues. Block grants are one time spending packages distributed to communities or service agencies that are meant to help address specific issues that affect a community. While the federal government had block grants, the states, or Wisconsin in this instance, provide tax credits for worker housing as a way of taking the weight off the shoulders of the already impoverished. She says that social service issues are in the power of how the county utilizes them, which is especially why it falls into their hands to address issues related to the services. I asked her what we as individuals can do to fight unhousedness, and she said that we honestly can't do much alone, but she said “we can have empathy”. She encourages volunteering at homeless shelters and other organisations poised to fight unhousedness as a way to work to end unhousedness on an individual level.

I asked Rep. Sinicki about how the Democratic Party of Milwaukee seeks to address the unhoused issue, because she is the head chair of the county party. She said that the Democrats host food drives and a Christmas toy drive as volunteer commitments besides the legislation that they already introduce to the city of Milwaukee and the state itself. She said that the Democratic Party works with Mr. Bob's Under the Bridge for their unhousedness volunteering and organizing donations. She says that they specifically need donations for clothes and suitcases. She also said that the Wisconsin Republican Party often does media stunts or photo ops at homeless shelters, but doesn't make contributions or effort to solve or address the issue in most cases.

I brought up how much of a factor discrimination and racism play in the potential of being unhousedness, and she says that it plays the biggest role for minorities. Rep. Sinicki said, “we are still a very racist state and country.” She brings up that generational education issues continue to cause issues for many minorities. She says that many older generations simply didn't have the time to invest their time into education or like many others, education was made very difficult to access. Segregation in the United States is often fixated on the American south, which has had a long and storied history with oppressing and discriminating against its large African American population. When segregation and civil rights are brought up it is often with a fixated lens on the American south, but the reality that is often overlooked is that segregation was instituted across

many states outside of the American south and in states that are often seen as northern. Milwaukee, which has often been described as one of the most segregated cities in the United States is a perfect example of this racial division. Little are segregated schools in Wisconsin brought up, said Christine Sinicki, which absolutely plays a role in the division in education between minorities. Another attributor of unhousedness in Milwaukee but especially across the country is that minorities are often subject to low wages due to discrimination. In fact some employers seek to employ illegal immigrants because they can be much more easily paid illegally low wages, because if they were to complain they could be just as easily deported to their home country. She said that instead of addressing the issue of the racial division with unhousedness, we need to address the root of the problem. A lack of homes, easier access to get them, livable wages, and an educational emphasis in order to prevent generations from continuing the cycle of unhousedness. She said that there are many people who have to live paycheck to paycheck and that with the slightest fluctuation in the economy could be pushed out of their homes and onto the street. She also said that although education helps prevent unhousedness, it isn't a guarantor, and she says that there are many highly educated people who are unhoused.

Towards the end of our interview, I asked Rep. Sinicki how she believes that we reached our current state of the unhoused crisis and how we even arrived at the issue in the first place. She said that unhousedness didn't become a real issue in the United States until the 1980s, which coincided with the corporate exodus of American companies in their search to find cheaper labor overseas. She said that while unhousedness was an issue before, politicians and the larger population didn't begin to take notice until it began to affect white people as well or began to affect their pocket books. She said that most people don't bat an eye at an African American or other minority who is unhoused, but they started to take notice when they began to see more and more white people in the streets.

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